

Orbital Shrinking: Theory and Applications

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Abstract

We present a method, based on formulation symmetry, for generating Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) relaxations with fewer variables than the original symmetric MILP. Our technique also extends to convex MINLP, and some nonconvex MINLP with a special structure. We showcase the effectiveness of our relaxation when embedded in a decomposition method applied to two important applications (multi-activity shift scheduling and multiple knapsack problem), showing that it can improve CPU times by several orders of magnitude compared to pure MIP or CP approaches.

Keywords: Mathematical programming, constraint programming, discrete optimization, symmetry, relaxation, MINLP

1. Introduction

Branch-and-Bound (BB) type methods often become very slow when the solution set is symmetric (Gent et al., 2006; Margot, 2010), due to the explorations of many symmetric subtrees. Given a Mathematical Programming (MP) formulation, we distinguish the automorphism group of its solution set (called the *solution group*) and the group of variable symmetries fixing the formulation (called the *formulation group*). The latter is usually defined as the group of variable index permutations which keep the objective function invariant, the right-hand-side constraint vector invariant, and permutes the order of the constraints (Cohen et al., 2005; Margot, 2002). It is very easy to show that the formulation group is a subgroup of the solution group.

Finding a universal technique for determining the solution group automatically would imply knowing the solution set *a priori*, which would make the optimization problem moot. On the other hand, various techniques for finding the formulation group of a Constraint Satisfaction Program (CSP) and of a MP have been proposed in the literature (Bödi et al., 2013; Liberti, 2008, 2012;

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Puget, 2005). The most efficient methods reduce to the graph isomorphism problem, which can be solved in practice using tools such as `nauty` (McKay, 2007).

Once some symmetries are known, they can be exploited in a variety of ways. In Constraint Programming (CP) and Mixed-Integer Programming (MIP), a common technique consists in trying to make some of the symmetric solutions infeasible by:

- adjoining Symmetry-Breaking Constraints (SBC) to the original formulation (Liberti, 2012; Liberti and Ostrowski, 2014; Smith, 2010);
- using a clever branching strategy in constraint propagation (Gent and Smith, 2000) or in BB (e.g. isomorphism pruning (Margot, 2002, 2003) or orbital branching (Ostrowski et al., 2008, 2011a)).

In Semidefinite Programming (SDP), due to the fact that decision variables are matrices, symmetry can be exploited very naturally through group representation theory. This yields formulations with fewer variables (in fact, the variable matrix becomes block-diagonal) but having the same optimum (Gatermann and Parrilo, 2004).

A different approach is proposed in (Bödi et al., 2013), where solving an Integer Linear Program (ILP) with a highly transitive solution group is essentially reduced to a line search in a lattice. The proposed method is very innovative, but most practically occurring ILPs have groups that are very far from being transitive. A generalization of this approach which aims to relax the requirement for high transitivity is given in (Herr et al., 2013). Although applicability remains limited, this technique was used in solving the instance `toll-like` in the MIPLIB2010 library (Koch et al., 2011), which was previously unsolved.

We propose another approach, called *Orbital Shrinking* (OS), for exploiting symmetry in MILP and certain subclasses of Mixed-Integer Nonlinear Programming (MINLP). Orbital shrinking is a relaxation technique: given a MIP P and a subgroup G of its formulation (or solution) group, it replaces each orbit of variables by a single variable. Therefore, OS produces compact MIP relaxations. If G is transitive, and hence has only one orbit, the resulting MIP is trivial, because it has only one variable. At the other extreme, if G is the trivial group, then there are as many orbits as there are variables, and the relaxation is the same as the original MIP.

To solve problems exactly, we employ the OS relaxation (OSR) in a general purpose decomposition framework, which we apply to two real-life applications: multi-activity shift scheduling and multiple knapsack problems. OS decomposition naturally provides a new way for designing hybrid MIP/CP decompositions: our computational results show that the resulting method can be orders of magnitude faster than pure MIP or CP approaches.

The outline of the paper is as follows. In Section 1.1, we review some main results on symmetry groups in the context of optimization problems. Then, in Section 2, we present orbital shrinking, and show that it yields a relaxation of the original problem. In Section 3 we analyze differences and similarities between

OS and core point algorithms. In Section 4 we describe a general decomposition framework based on orbital shrinking, while in Sections 5 and 6 we specialize the general framework to multi-activity shift scheduling and multiple knapsack problems, also reporting computational results. Conclusions are finally drawn in Section 7.

We assume the reader is familiar with mixed-integer programming, constraint programming and basic group theory. The present paper extends and is based on the preliminary results presented in (Fischetti and Liberti, 2012; Salvagnin, 2013; Salvagnin and Walsh, 2012), by the same authors.

1.1. Some notation and terminology

Let P be an arbitrary MINLP of the form

$$\begin{aligned} \min f(x) & \tag{1} \\ \forall i \in C \quad g_i(x) & \leq 0 & \tag{2} \\ \forall j \in J \quad x_j & \in \mathbb{Z} & \tag{3} \end{aligned}$$

where $J \subseteq [n] = \{1, \dots, n\}$ is the subset of integer variables. Without loss of generality, the objective function $f(x)$ is assumed to be convex.

We consider the formulation group G_P of P , containing the set of permutations $\pi \in S_n$ that leave the formulation of P unchanged, except for a possible reordering of the constraints. The practical applicability of this definition extends to Linear Programs (LP) and MILPs. With MINLPs, we restrict our attention to functional forms which are closed with respect to the usual operators $(+, -, \times, \div, (\cdot)^a)$ and unary functions (\log, \exp) . These expressions are easily represented by trees, and whole MINLP formulations can be represented by suitable Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAG) (Belotti et al., 2009). G_P is then obtained as a restriction of the automorphism group of this DAG to the set of variable indices of P (Liberti, 2012). G_P can be computed by means of any graph isomorphism package such as Nauty (McKay, 1981) or Saucy (Katebi et al., 2010): these both implement backtracking algorithms which are exponential-time in the worst case, but which are sufficiently fast in practice to be of use.

Any subgroup G of G_P partitions the set of variables into equivalence classes called *orbits* via its natural action: two variable indices i, j are in the same class if there is $g \in G$ such that $g(i) = j$. We denote by Ω_G the *orbital partition* of the action of G on $[n]$. We remark that, by definition, integer and continuous variables cannot be permuted with each other, so each orbit contains only integer or only continuous variables. Constraints of P are themselves partitioned into equivalence classes, called *constraint orbits*: in particular, two constraints are in the same orbit if and only if one is mapped into the other (because of reordering) when some variable permutation $\pi \in G$ is applied. Finally, given a subset $I \subseteq [n]$, the *point-wise stabilizer* $G[I]$ of G with respect to I is the subgroup of G consisting of permutations π such that $\pi(i) = i$ for all $i \in I$.

2. Orbital Shrinking Relaxation

The OS relaxation with respect to a subgroup G of its formulation group could be best described as “formulation modulo G ”, as it replaces entire orbits by single variables. In this section, we will describe how to construct the OSR of a given optimization problem P , and show that this is indeed a relaxation of the original problem.

The first step is to classify variables and constraints according to their incidence and (non)linearity/convexity. Specifically, the subgroup G defining the OSR will be taken with respect to a certain subgroup of G_P rather than the whole of G_P , as defined below. Let us consider a partition (V_1, V_2) and (C_1, C_2, C_3) of the variables and constraints of P , respectively, which satisfies the following conditions:

- all constraints in C_1 are convex w.r.t. the variables in V_1 (in other words, once the variables in V_2 are fixed);
- all constraints in C_2 are functions of sums of variables along the orbits defined by the group $G_P[V_2]$, the point-wise stabilizer of G_P w.r.t. V_2 ;
- C_3 consists of all constraints not in C_1 or C_2 .

The meaning of the constraint partition will become clear in the following; a remark is given after Corollary 2.6. Also note that, by definition, $G_P[V_2]$ is a group of variable permutations acting on V_1 . Now let G be a subgroup of $G_P[V_2]$ and $\Omega = \Omega_G$ be the orbital partition of $[n]$ induced by G .

Given a problem P and such a partition $(V_1, V_2, C_1, C_2, C_3)$, we define the orbital shrinking reformulation P_{OSR} as the MP formulation obtained by the following procedure:

- for each $\omega \in \Omega$, define a variable z_ω , constrained to be integer if and only if the orbit ω consists of integer variables; let $z = (z_\omega \mid \omega \in \Omega)$;
- for each constraint $g_i(x) \leq 0$ in $C_1 \cup C_2$, define a new constraint $\bar{g}_i(z) \leq 0$, obtained from $g_i(x) \leq 0$ through the formal substitution:

$$x_j \rightarrow \frac{z_\omega}{|\omega|} \quad (4)$$

for all $j \in \omega$;

- define the objective function $\bar{f}(z)$ as the result of applying to $f(x)$ the same formal substitution (4);
- ignore constraints in C_3 .

Next, we show that P_{OSR} is a relaxation of P .

Lemma 2.1 is a basic generalization of Burnside’s Lemma (Rotman, 2002): we suspect it exists in the group theory literature, but we were not able to find it. Since the applicability to *any* function ψ makes the lemma interesting in its own right, we decided to provide a proof.

2.1 Lemma

Let $\omega \in \Omega$ and ψ be any function with $\text{dom } \psi = [n]$. Then

$$\sum_{\pi \in G} \psi(\pi(j)) = \frac{|G|}{|\omega|} \sum_{l \in \omega} \psi(l) \quad \forall j \in \omega. \quad (5)$$

Proof. For any $l \in \omega$, let $T_{jl} = \{\pi \in G : \pi(j) = l\}$. It is easy to show that $|T_{jl}| = |G[j]|$ (recall $G[j]$ is the point-wise stabilizer of j) for all $l \in \omega$: given an arbitrary $\pi \in T_{jl}$, we can define the map $\phi : G[j] \rightarrow T_{jl}$ as $\sigma \rightarrow \pi\sigma$ for any $\sigma \in G[j]$. This map is a bijection, with inverse $\phi^{-1} : \sigma \rightarrow \pi^{-1}\sigma$, so the two sets have the same cardinality. Hence

$$\sum_{\pi \in G} \psi(\pi(j)) = \sum_{l \in \omega} \sum_{\pi \in T_{jl}} \psi(\pi(j)) = \sum_{l \in \omega} |T_{jl}| \psi(l) = \frac{|G|}{|\omega|} \sum_{l \in \omega} \psi(l),$$

where the last equality is justified by the orbit-stabilizer theorem. \square

Corollary 2.2 is an application of Lemma 2.1 to the *barycenter* (Bödi et al., 2013) of the group action, also called group average (Gatermann and Parrilo, 2004) or Reynolds operator (Sturmfels, 2008).

2.2 Corollary

Let x^* be an arbitrary feasible solution of P , and consider the convex combination \bar{x} defined as

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{|G|} \sum_{\pi \in G} \pi(x^*) \quad (6)$$

Then, for each $\omega \in \Omega$ and $j \in \omega$, we have

$$\bar{x}_j = \frac{1}{|\omega|} \sum_{l \in \omega} x_l^*. \quad (7)$$

Proof. Define a function $X : [n] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as $X(j) = x_j^*$. Applying Lemma 2.1 we get:

$$\bar{x}_j = \frac{1}{|G|} \sum_{\pi \in G} x_{\pi(j)}^* = \frac{1}{|G|} \sum_{\pi \in G} X(\pi(j)) = \frac{1}{|\omega|} \sum_{l \in \omega} X(l) = \frac{1}{|\omega|} \sum_{l \in \omega} x_l^*.$$

\square

Lemma 2.3 is well known, and basically states that the barycenter is an invariant of the group action (Sturmfels, 2008). We provide a proof for completeness, since it is very short.

2.3 Lemma

Let x^* be an arbitrary feasible solution of P . Then, for any $\pi \in G$ and for any $\omega \in \Omega$

$$\sum_{j \in \omega} x_j^* = \sum_{j \in \omega} \pi(x^*)_j = \sum_{j \in \omega} \bar{x}_j.$$

Proof. By definition, all permutations in G map variables in ω to other variables in ω , so the sums of the variables in a given orbit is invariant to permutations in G . This proves the first equality. The second equality follows by definition of \bar{x} (see Eq. (6)). \square

Finally, we prove that P_{OSR} is a relaxation. We recall that the P_{OSR} formulation involves an objective function $\bar{f}(z)$ and constraints $\bar{g}(z) \leq 0$.

2.4 Theorem

P_{OSR} is a relaxation of P .

Proof. Let x^* be an arbitrary feasible solution of P . We will show that there always exists a point z^* feasible for P_{OSR} and such that $\bar{f}(z^*) \leq f(x^*)$, hence the claim. Given x^* , let us construct the two points \bar{x} and z^* as

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{|G|} \sum_{\pi \in G} \pi(x^*) \quad (8)$$

$$\forall \omega \in \Omega \quad z_\omega^* = \sum_{j \in \omega} x_j^*. \quad (9)$$

For each constraint in C_1 , $g_i(\bar{x}) \leq 0$ because $\bar{x}[V_2] = x^*[V_2]$ and g_i is convex in V_1 . Similarly, for each constraint in C_2 , we have $g_i(\bar{x}) = g_i(x^*) \leq 0$ because of Lemma 2.3. So, all constraint in $C_1 \cup C_2$ are satisfied by \bar{x} .

Now let us consider z^* . The integrality requirements on z are automatically satisfied, as x^* is a feasible solution of P , and thus sums of integer values within an orbit yield an integer result. In addition, for each constraint in $C_1 \cup C_2$, we have by definition and by Corollary 2.2

$$\bar{g}_i(z^*) = g_i(\bar{x}) \leq 0$$

since x^* itself is feasible for those constraints. Finally, we need no check on any constraint in C_3 , as those are not part of P_{OSR} . As far as the objective function is concerned, we have $\bar{f}(z^*) = f(\bar{x}) \leq f(x^*)$ where the equality is by definition of $\bar{f}(z)$ and Corollary 2.2, while the inequality is by convexity of $f(x)$ and because \bar{x} is a convex combination of solutions with the same cost (by symmetry). \square

Corollary 2.5 essentially follows because the barycenter is a group invariant, and is at the basis of the ideas developed in (Bödi et al., 2013; Gatermann and Parrilo, 2004; Herr et al., 2013).

2.5 Corollary

If P is a convex optimization problem, then P_{OSR} is an exact reformulation of P .

Proof. In the convex case, we have $J = C_2 = C_3 = V_2 = \emptyset$. Given an optimal solution z^* of P_{OSR} , we can construct a point x^* as

$$x_j^* = \frac{z_\omega^*}{|\omega|}$$

which, by convexity of constraints, is feasible for P and has the same objective value as z^* . The result easily follows. \square

Corollary 2.6 shows the easiest case where P_{OSR} is an exact reformulation.

2.6 Corollary

If there exists an optimal solution x^ of P such that $|\omega|$ divides $\sum_{j \in \omega} x_j^*$ for all orbits ω associated to integer variables, and $C_3 = \emptyset$, then P_{OSR} is an exact reformulation of P .*

Proof. In this case, the point x^* constructed as in the previous corollary is also integer, and satisfies all the constraints of P . It is then feasible for P and thus optimal. \square

2.1. Remarks

- Cor. 2.6 applies, for instance, in case a standard ILP model for the asymmetric Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) is solved on symmetric input arc costs. In this setting, the group action induces an orbit $\{(i, j), (j, i)\}$ for each node pair $\{i, j\}$, and orbital shrinking automatically produces the symmetric TSP formulation of the problem — which is of course a much better way to model it when costs are symmetric. In this context, orbital shrinking can be seen as an automatic preprocessing step to produce a more effective model for the actual input data.
- The set C_3 of constraints is provided to give freedom in the choice of which variables to put into V_2 . Intuitively, for a non-convex constraint we have a choice between ignoring it completely in the orbital shrinking relaxation and stabilizing its variables, which is clearly stronger but may reduce the shrinking possibilities considerably. In addition, we note that the partition (C_1, C_2, C_3) is by definition consistent with the constraint orbits of P and that all constraints in the same orbit will be mapped to the same constraint in P_{OSR} , so in practice P_{OSR} has one variable for each variable orbit and one constraint for each constraint orbit in P associated with a constraint in $C_1 \cup C_2$.
- The convexity of the constraints in C_1 is crucial for the above arguments. Indeed, given an arbitrary MINLP, a direct formal substitution according to (4) does not yield a relaxation in general, as shown in the following example.

2.7 Example

Let the feasible set of P be defined as

$$\{(x_1, x_2) \mid (x_1 - x_2)(x_2 - x_1) \leq -1\}$$

This set is not empty and the two variables are clearly symmetric. However, with the formal substitution $x_i \rightarrow z/2$ we obtain the set

$$\{z \mid 0 \leq -1\}$$

which is empty.

- The constraints in C_2 can be convex or nonconvex, as long as their arguments are sums of original variables over the group orbits: essentially, they carry over to the OSR unchanged, aside from the replacement of orbital sums by the corresponding z variable.

3. The role of the barycenter

In this section we discuss the relationships between OSR and other existing methods for exploiting symmetry in MP based on core points. All of these methods are based on the concept of the *barycenter* of the group action, defined in Eq. (6).

The papers (Bödi et al., 2013; Herr et al., 2013) discuss a new approach to optimize symmetric MILP (or convex MINLP). The first paper (Bödi et al., 2013) requires G_P to be at least transitive on $[n]$ (i.e. its action on $[n]$ consists of a single orbit). This requirement is partly relaxed the second paper (Bödi et al., 2013): G_P is only assumed to have a direct product of (possibly trivial) symmetric groups as a subgroup.¹

Let P be the ILP $\max\{c^\top x \mid Ax \leq b \wedge x \in \mathbb{Z}^n\}$, and let $G \leq G_P$ have a transitive action on $[n]$. The papers (Bödi et al., 2013; Herr et al., 2013) consider a decomposition of the feasible region \mathcal{F} of P in the *fixed subset* $F_G = \{x \in \mathcal{F} \mid \forall g \in G (gx = x)\}$ (its span is called the *fixed subspace*) and the affine subspaces $H_c^k = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid c^\top x = k\}$, where $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, which contain the level sets. Without loss of generality, c is assumed to be a coprime integral vector, i.e. one whose components have unit greatest common divisor. It is shown in (Bödi et al., 2013) that $\{H_c^k \mid k \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ is a partition of \mathbb{Z}^n for each coprime c .

In (Bödi et al., 2013), G is assumed to be transitive: by definition, this implies that for each $i \neq j \in [n]$ there is $\pi \in G$ mapping c_i to c_j , yielding c to be a scaling of the all-one vector $\mathbf{1}$. Enters the barycenter: since it is invariant with respect to the action of G , it spans the fixed subspace. By definition, the barycenter is a scaled sum of all the orbit elements (see Eq. (7)), and hence, by the same reasoning as the one carried out for c , it is also a scaled version of $\mathbf{1}$. In particular, the span of c is equal to the fixed subspace; and, moreover, each affine subspace H_c^k is orthogonal to the fixed subspace.

The fact that F_G aligns precisely with the objective function direction is obviously as rare as full transitivity of G , but it pays off handsomely: if y is

¹We remark that the instance library data given in (Liberti, 2012) shows that many formulation groups are *isomorphic* to products of symmetric groups. Further analysis, however, shows that in most cases formulation groups are *not* themselves products of symmetric groups.

an optimal solution of the continuous relaxation, then the barycenter $\zeta \mathbf{1}$ (where $\zeta = \frac{1}{n} \sum_j y_j$) is also optimal, so $\lfloor \zeta \rfloor \mathbf{1}$ is a feasible integer point; hence the ILP optimal value must be at least as large as that of $\lfloor \zeta \rfloor \mathbf{1}$, namely $\lfloor \zeta \rfloor n$. Trivially, we also have $\lfloor \zeta n \rfloor$ as an upper bound. Hence it suffices to find an integer feasible point in H_c^k for the largest possible k in $K = \{\lfloor \zeta \rfloor n, \dots, \lfloor \zeta n \rfloor\}$. In (Bödi et al., 2013), Alg. A suggests a direct search for decreasing values of k (an obvious $\log(|K|)$ improvement could be given by using bisection on K).

In general, the subproblem of (Bödi et al., 2013, Alg. A), which consists of finding an integer feasible point in each H_c^k , is hard. However, if G is μ -transitive (with $\mu \geq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$), then the integer feasible points in H_c^k that are closest to the fixed subspace, called *core points*, can be found in polynomial time (Bödi et al., 2013, Alg. B). Transitivity rarely occurs in practical problems; and μ -transitivity, requiring the existence of permutations mapping any μ -tuple to any other, is even rarer.

The paper (Herr et al., 2013), subsequent to (Bödi et al., 2013), relaxes the transitivity requirements, generalizes the definition of a core point, and proposes two algorithms for solving symmetric MILPs and convex MINLPs. The first algorithm is a generalization of the core point algorithm of (Bödi et al., 2013): to address the fact that $c = \mathbf{1}$ is no longer the unique generator of the fixed subspace, (Herr et al., 2013, Alg. A) still solves integer feasibility subproblems on H_c^k but also checks their objective function values. The second algorithm is based on a smart parametrization of generalized core points, and the fact that it is sufficient to find an optimal core point. It turns out that this parametrization results in a reformulation of the original problem. As mentioned above, the requirement on G for these algorithms to work is that it should be a direct product of symmetric group $S_{k_1} \times \dots \times S_{k_d}$. The reformulation adds new sets of variables: $t_i \in \mathbb{Z}$ for each $i \leq d$, and $s_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$ for each $i \leq d$ and $j < k_i$; and new sets of constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall i \leq d \quad x_{ij} &= t_i \mathbf{1}_{k_i} + \sum_{j < k_i} s_{ij} \mathbf{c}_j \\ \forall i \leq d \quad \sum_{j < k_i} s_{ij} &\leq 1, \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{1}_{k_i}$ is the all-one vector of size k_i , $\mathbf{c}_j = \sum_{h \leq j} e_h$ (with e_h the h -th unit vector of the standard basis of \mathbb{R}^n) is a representative of the core set of H_c^j , and the components of x have been appropriately re-indexed using i, j . The original variables x can then be eliminated using the equivalent expressions in the t and s variables.

Here are the main differences between OSR and core point algorithms:

- OSR does not make *any* assumption on the structure of G , other than it should be nontrivial, whereas core points algorithms make strong assumptions on G ;
- OSR is a relaxation method, i.e. it acts on the formulation, whereas the core point algorithms in (Bödi et al., 2013) do not;

- the reformulation derived in the second core point algorithm in (Herr et al., 2013) is exact, and, in particular, different from the OS relaxation.

The only similarity between the OSR and the results in (Bödi et al., 2013) is that the fixed subspace LP reformulation (Bödi et al., 2013, Eq. (3)) is the same as the OS relaxation whenever there are no integer variables (see Cor. 2.5). The only similarity with (Herr et al., 2013) is that the barycenter is the point of departure to derive a reformulation of the original MIP.

4. Orbital Shrinking decomposition

Let P be a MINLP as in the previous sections and let G be the chosen formulation subgroup for P . Using G , we can construct the OSR P_{OSR} of P , which will act as the master problem in our decomposition scheme, much like in a traditional Benders decomposition scheme. Indeed, the scheme is akin to a logic-based Benders decomposition (Hooker and Ottosson, 2003), although the decomposition is not based on a traditional variable splitting, but on aggregation, and the OSR master works with the aggregated variables z . A similar approach, although problem specific, was also used in (Linderöth et al., 2009; Ostrowski et al., 2011b). Note that the technique is general as a framework, not as a black-box algorithm that can be readily applied to an arbitrary instance, in the same way as logic-based Benders is: in both cases some problem-specific knowledge must be exploited for the method to succeed.

4.1. The slave feasibility problem

For each feasible solution z^* of P_{OSR} , we can then define the following (slave) feasibility check problem $R(z^*)$

$$\forall i \in C \quad g_i(x) \leq 0 \tag{10}$$

$$\forall \omega \in \Omega \quad \sum_{j \in \omega} x_j = z_\omega^* \tag{11}$$

$$\forall j \in J \quad x_j \in \mathbb{Z} \tag{12}$$

If $R(z^*)$ is feasible, then the aggregated solution z^* can be *disaggregated* into a feasible solution x^* of P , with the same cost. Otherwise, z^* must be removed from P_{OSR} , in either of the following two ways:

1. Generate a *nogood* cut that forbids the assignment z^* to the z variables. As in logic-based Benders decomposition, an ad-hoc study of the problem is needed to derive (strong) nogood cuts.
2. Branching. As z^* is integer, branching on non-fractional z variables is needed, and z^* will still be a feasible solution in one of the two child nodes. However, the method would still converge, because the number of variables is finite and the search tree has finite depth, assuming that z variables are bounded. Note that in this case the method may repeatedly

check for feasibility the same aggregated solution z^* : in practice, this can easily be avoided by keeping a list (cache) of recently checked aggregated solutions with the corresponding feasibility status.

4.2. Symmetry of the slave problem

It is important to note that, by construction, problem $R(z^*)$ may also have a nontrivial formulation group.

4.1 Lemma

The group G used to generate P_{OSR} is a subgroup of the formulation group G_R of $R(z^*)$.

Proof. Let P be the MP formulation (1)-(3), and $\pi \in G \leq G_P$. Then π stabilizes the constraints (2) of P , which appear in $R(z^*)$ as (10). Since constraints (11) are generated by means of the action of G , π fixes each orbit of this action, and hence π also stabilizes (11). Thus $\pi \in G_R$ as claimed. \square

On the other hand, G_R could be a subgroup of G_P or vice versa, or be such that $G_R = G_P$, depending on the value of z^* , on the action of G and on the objective function of P .

4.2 Example

Let P be the problem $\max\{\sum_{i=1}^5 x_i \mid \sum_{i=1}^5 x_i \leq 1 \wedge \forall i \leq 5 x_i \in \{0, 1\}\}$: we have $G_P \cong S_5$. Consider the subgroup $G = \langle (1, 2), (3, 4), (3, 5) \rangle \cong C_2 \times S_3$, having the two orbits $\{1, 2\}$ and $\{3, 4, 5\}$. Then $R(z^*)$ is:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 &\leq 1 \\ x_1 + x_2 &= z_1^* \\ x_3 + x_4 + x_5 &= z_2^*, \end{aligned}$$

which, for any feasible z^* , has formulation group $G_R = G$, a proper subgroup of G_P . Obviously, by modifying P so that the objective is $x_1 + x_2 + 2(x_3 + x_4 + x_5)$ we have $G_P = G$ and hence $G_R = G_P$.

4.3 Example

Let P be the problem

$$\max \left\{ \sum_{i \leq 3} x_i + 2 \sum_{4 \leq i \leq 6} x_i \mid \sum_{i \leq 6} x_i \leq 6 \wedge \forall i \leq 6 x_i \in \{0, 1\} \right\},$$

and take $x^* = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$ as the optimal solution, with corresponding P_{OSR} solution z^* . We have $G_P = \langle (1, 2), (1, 3), (4, 5), (4, 6) \rangle \cong S_3 \times S_3$. Consider

$G = G_P$, having two orbits $\{1, 2, 3\}$ and $\{4, 5, 6\}$. Then $z^* = (3, 3)$ and $R(z^*)$ is:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + x_6 &\leq 6 \\ x_1 + x_2 + x_3 &= 3 \\ x_4 + x_5 + x_6 &= 3. \end{aligned}$$

The formulation group G_R certainly contains all of the permutations of $G_P = G$ (as per Lemma 4.1), and also the permutation $(1, 4)(2, 5)(3, 6)$, which is not in G_P , and makes $G_R \cong (S_3 \times S_3) \rtimes C_2$. So in this case G_P is a proper subgroup of G_R .

Having a non trivial symmetry group in $R(z^*)$ does not necessarily make the problem harder to solve, as it can be used to further simplify the problem or solving it more efficiently. In addition (i) linking constraints (11) may make the model much easier to solve, and (ii) the easier structure of $R(z^*)$ may allow for more effective symmetry breaking techniques. Still, it must be taken into account when devising an effective orbital shrinking decomposition.

Note also that $R(z^*)$ is a pure feasibility problem, so a CP solver may be a better choice than a MINLP solver. In addition, the method intuitively allows symmetry to be exploited twice: once in the (symmetry-free) master, where P_{OSR} effectively enumerates equivalence classes of solutions of P , and once in each slave, where more traditional symmetry breaking techniques, such as orbital branching or isomorphism pruning can be used.

4.3. Dealing with continuous variables

The above decomposition strategy is well suited for pure integer problems, but is not very convenient when continuous variables are present in the model because in the mixed-integer case one should enumerate, in the master, all possible values also for the continuous variables, which makes the method impractical. However, the method can be modified to deal with continuous variables more effectively. In particular, we can:

- zero out the objective coefficients of the z_ω variables in P_{OSR} ;
- reintroduce the objective coefficients of the continuous variables in $R(z^*)$;
- remove the linking constraints (11) associated to orbits of continuous variables.

The advantage of the above modification is that only the partial assignments over the aggregated integer variables need to be checked, at the expense of turning the feasibility check into an optimization problem itself. Such extended method has been used in (Mittelmann and Salvagnin, 2015) to solve a very challenging instance of 3-dimensional quadratic assignment problem. Interestingly, the role of MIP and CP was swapped in (Mittelmann and Salvagnin, 2015): a CP solver was used to enumerate all feasible solutions of the master problem, while a MIP solver was used to solve the optimization slaves.

5. Application to Shift Scheduling

A shift scheduling problem assigns a feasible working shift to a set of employees, in order to satisfy the demands for a given set of activities at each period in a given time horizon. The set of feasible shifts that can be assigned to employees is often defined by a complex set of work regulation agreements and other rules. Assigning a shift to an employee means specify an activity for each period, which may be a working activity or a rest activity (e.g., lunch). The objective is usually to minimize the cost of the schedule, which is usually a linear combination of working costs plus some penalties for undercovering/overcovering the demands of the activities in each time period.

In particular, suppose we are given a planning horizon divided into a set of periods T , a set of activities A , a subset $W \subset A$ of working activities, and a set of employees E . For each period $t \in T$ and for each working activity $a \in W$, we are given a demand d_{at} , an assignment cost c_{at} , an undercovering cost c_{at}^- and an overcovering cost c_{at}^+ . Introducing the set of integer variables y_{at} , which count the number of employees assigned to activity a at period t , and integer variables s_{at}^-, s_{at}^+ that count the appropriate under/over covering, we can formulate the problem as:

$$\min \sum_{a \in W} \sum_{t \in T} c_{at} y_{at} + \sum_{a \in W} \sum_{t \in T} c_{at}^+ s_{at}^+ + \sum_{a \in W} \sum_{t \in T} c_{at}^- s_{at}^- \quad (13)$$

$$\forall a \in W, t \in T \quad y_{at} - s_{at}^+ + s_{at}^- = d_{at} \quad (14)$$

$$\forall a \in W, t \in T \quad \sum_{e \in E} x_{eat} = y_{at} \quad (15)$$

$$\forall e \in E \quad \langle x \text{ defines a feasible shift} \rangle \quad (16)$$

$$\forall a \in W, t \in T \quad y_{at}, s_{at}^+, s_{at}^- \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \quad (17)$$

$$\forall e \in E, a \in W, t \in T \quad x_{eat} \in \{0, 1\} \quad (18)$$

where x_{eat} are binary variables, each of which is equal to 1 if employee e is assigned to activity a in period t . Model (13)-(18) is symmetric because employees are assumed to be identical, so with $|E|$ employees we have a symmetry group of order $|E|!$. As for orbits, each orbit contains all the variables for all employees associated with a given entity (for example, for each activity a and time period t we have an orbit containing the variables x_{*at}).

A convenient way to define the set of feasible shifts that can be assigned to a given employee is to use a regular or a context-free language, i.e., the set of feasible shifts can be viewed as the words accepted by a finite automaton or, more generally, by a push-down automaton. It has been shown in (Côté et al., 2011a; Pesant et al., 2009) that it is possible to derive a polyhedron that describes a given regular/context-free language. Such representations are compact (in an appropriate extended space, i.e., introducing additional variables) and thus lead directly to a MIP formulation of the problem. In particular, the extended formulation for a regular language is essentially a network flow formulation based on the expanded graph associated with the accepting automaton (Côté et al.,

2011a; Pesant, 2004). The extended formulation for the context-free language, on the other hand, is based on an and-or graph built by the standard CYK parser (Hopcroft and Ullman, 1979) for the corresponding grammar (Pesant et al., 2009; Quimper and Walsh, 2007).

Note that it is not necessary to describe completely the set of feasible shifts by a regular/context-free language. The formal language may capture only some of the constraints defining a feasible shift, with the remaining ones described as linear inequalities. This may simplify the corresponding automaton considerably (for example, regular languages are notoriously bad at handling counting arguments). However, describing the set of feasible shifts with formal languages alone has some important implications. First of all, it has been proven for both the regular and context-free languages that the derived polyhedron is integral (Pesant et al., 2009), and thus, if there are no other constraints, it is possible to optimize a linear function over the set of feasible shifts by solving just a linear program. Even more importantly, these results have been extended also to polyhedra describing sets of feasible shifts (Côté et al., 2011b). It is then possible to consider an aggregated (*implicit*) model and reconstruct an optimal solution of the original one with a polynomial post-processing phase. From the OSR point of view, this means that P_{OSR} is in this case an exact reformulation. Consider for example the regular polytope in its extended form: the optimal solution is always a flow of integral value, say k , and basic network flow theory guarantees that it can be decomposed into k paths of unitary flow (and since each path in the expanded graph corresponds to a word in the language, this is a feasible solution for the original explicit problem). Similar reasoning applies to the grammar polytope (although it is not a flow model), as successfully shown in (Côté et al., 2011b). It is interesting to note that this gives the current state-of-the-art for solving multi-activity shift scheduling problems.

Unfortunately, it is not always reasonable to describe the set of feasible shifts completely with a formal language. While it is true that formal languages can be extended without changing the complexity of the corresponding MIP encoding (this is particularly true for context-free languages (Quimper and Walsh, 2007)), still some cardinality constraints may be very awkward to express, as shown in the following example taken from (Salvagnin and Walsh, 2012).

5.1 Example

Let's consider a time horizon of 18 hours, divided into 18 periods. A feasible shift is a word of length 18 build from the alphabet $\Sigma = \{a, b, r\}$ (where a denotes the only working activity, r is a rest period, while b is a break period) that follows the pattern rest-work-break-work-break-work-break-work-rest. Suppose that the breaks are constrained to be one period long, and the number of working periods must be between 6 and 8. Then, a very simple grammar encoding the set of feasible shifts, ignoring the cardinality constraint, is:

$$\begin{aligned} S &\rightarrow RFR & F &\rightarrow PBP & P &\rightarrow WBW \\ R &\rightarrow Rr|r & W &\rightarrow Wa|a & B &\rightarrow b \end{aligned}$$

In this particular case, since the number of breaks in the shift is fixed (3), it is very easy to extend the grammar to deal with the cardinality constraint by restricting the production rule $F \rightarrow PBP$ to be applied only with substring of length between 9 and 11. This can be handled very well by the CYK parser, and thus the cardinality constraint can be added essentially at no cost.

However, let's consider a slightly more complicated case. The pattern of a feasible shift is the same, but now the length of breaks is not fixed to one. In particular, the number of break periods is constrained to be between 4 and 6. The best we can do keeping approximately the same grammar as before is the following (we use the notation of (Côté et al., 2011b) to indicate restrictions on production rules):

$$S \rightarrow RFR \quad F_{[10,14]} \rightarrow PBP \quad P_{[3,10]} \rightarrow WBW$$

$$R \rightarrow Rr|r \quad W \rightarrow Wa|a \quad B \rightarrow Bb|b$$

It is easy to see that the restrictions cannot be tightened any further, otherwise we may lose feasible shifts. However, the grammar also accepts the substring *rrababbbbbbaarr*, which violates both cardinality constraints.

The nature of the issues of the previous example is not exclusively theoretical: as the set of feasible shifts is finite, there always exists a regular/context-free language that describes that set. However, the corresponding automaton may be unreasonably large in practice. Note also that a very small change in the set of rules defining a feasible shift (like having a fixed or flexible amount of breaks, as in the example) can make the difference between being able to encode everything with a formal language or not.

In the following, we assume in the that the formal language captures the constraints that define the set of feasible shifts only partially, and thus we need to apply the decomposition framework of Section 4 in order to turn OSR into an exact procedure.

5.1. MIP model

The MIP model that we use is a simple modification of the general model (13)-(18). The main difference is that we partition the set of feasible shifts Ω into k subsets Ω_k , each of which is described by a potentially different deterministic finite automaton (DFA) and by cardinality constraints. This partition can simplify a lot the structure of the DFAs, and in general makes the implicit model more accurate, since the cardinality constraints are aggregated only within employees of the same "kind".

For each shift type Ω_k , the aggregated MIP model, i.e., the orbital shrinking relaxation that acts as our master problem, decides how many employees are assigned a shift in Ω_k , and then computes an aggregated integer flow of the same value.

5.2. CP checker

The decision to partition the set of feasible shifts into k subsets Ω_k has an important consequence on the structure of the CP checker: the model actually decomposes into k separate CP models, one for each type of shift. Given an index k , suppose the master (MIP) model assigns \bar{w}^k employees, with their aggregated shifts described by \bar{y}_{at} ; then the corresponding CP model can easily be formulated by using several *global constraints* (Rossi et al., 2006). Global constraints are used within a CP solver to represent general purpose and common substructures, for which efficient and effective constraint propagators are known. In our case, it turned out that, using standard global constraints from the literature and implementing some specific propagators for the model at hand (see (Salvagnin and Walsh, 2012) for details), the CP model was always extremely fast in proving whether the aggregated solution can be turned into a solution of the original model.

5.3. Computational Results

We tested our method on the multi-activity instances used in (Côté et al., 2011a,b; Quimper and Rousseau, 2010). This testbed is derived from a real-world store, and contains instances with 1 to 10 working activities (each class has 10 instances).

We implemented our method in C++, using IBM ILOG CPLEX 12.2 (CPLEX) as black box MIP solver, and Gecode 3.7.3 (Gecode Team, 2012) as CP solver. All tests have been performed on a PC with an Intel Core i5 CPU running at 2.66GHz, with 8GB of RAM (only one core was used by each process). Every method was given a time limit of 1 hour per instance. Concerning the set of feasible shifts Ω , we simply partitioned it into full-time and part-time shifts.

From the implementation point of view, our hybrid method is made of the following phases:

- First, the aggregated model is solved with CPLEX, using the default settings. The outcome of this (usually fast) first phase is a dual bound potentially stronger than the LP bound, and the set of aggregated solutions collected by the MIP solver during the solution process (not necessarily feasible for the original model).
- We apply an ad-hoc MIP repair/improve heuristic (Salvagnin and Walsh, 2012) to each aggregated solution which is within 20% ² of the aggregated model optimal solution. The outcome of this phase is always a feasible solution for the original model, thus a primal bound. Note that if the gap between the two is already below the 1% threshold, we are done.
- We solve the aggregated model again, this time implementing the hybrid MIP/CP approach described in Section 4. This means that we disable

²This threshold is used to avoid calling the repair/improve heuristic too many times.

dual reductions (otherwise the decomposition would not be correct) and use CPLEX callbacks framework to implement the decomposition.

Table 1 reports a comparison between the proposed method and others in the literature, for a number of activities from 1 to 10. `cpx-reg` refers to the explicit model based on the regular constraint in (Côté et al., 2011a), while `grammar` refers to the implicit model based on the grammar constraint in (Côté et al., 2011b). Note that for `grammar` we are reporting the results from (Côté et al., 2011b), which were obtained on a different machine and, more importantly, with an older version of CPLEX, so the numbers are meant to give just a reference. All methods were run to solve the instances to near-optimality, stopping when the final integrality gap dropped below 1%.

According to Table 1, `hybrid` outperforms significantly the explicit model `cpx-reg`, which scales very poorly because of symmetry issues and slow LPs. When compared to `grammar`, `hybrid` is very competitive only for up to 2 activities, while after that threshold `grammar` clearly takes the lead. This is somehow expected: the set of feasible shifts in these instances can indeed be described without too much effort with an extended grammar, and it is no surprise that the pure implicit MIP model outperforms our decomposition approach. However, `hybrid` is likely to be the best approach if the extended grammar is not a viable option.

Table 1: Average computing times between the different methods to solve to near-optimality (gap $\leq 1\%$) the instances with up to 10 activities.

# act.	# solved (10)			time(s)		
	<code>cpx-reg</code>	<code>hybrid</code>	<code>grammar</code>	<code>cpx-reg</code>	<code>hybrid</code>	<code>grammar</code>
1	10	10	10	41.3	9.1	283.7
2	9	10	9	707.9	194.5	379.9
3	4	5	9	2957.3	1996.4	205.4
4	3	6	10	2970.2	1827.9	300.5
5	0	8	10	3600.0	1438.4	146.2
6	1	4	10	3530.6	2340.6	213.8
7	1	6	10	3438.7	2399.0	230.9
8	0	5	10	3600.0	2201.5	257.1
9	0	4	10	3600.0	2444.0	289.1
10	0	2	10	3600.0	3275.6	516.7

Finally, Table 2 shows the gap just before the beginning of the last phase (but after the aggregated model has been solved and its solutions have been used to feed the MIP repair/improve heuristic). On almost all categories the average final gap is below 10%, with an average running time of 1 minute. This heuristic alone significantly outperforms `cpx-reg` for a number of activities greater than 3. It is also clear from the table that solving the OSR relaxations with a black

box MIP solver is usually very fast. Interestingly, solving these MIPs turns out to be often faster than solving the LP relaxations of the original models, while providing better or equal dual bounds.

Table 2: MIP repair/improve heuristics standalone results.

# act.	time(s)	gap(%)
1	6.2	1.5
2	46.5	6.5
3	24.7	20.3
4	30.3	7.1
5	34.5	5.9
6	33.5	10.5
7	63.2	7.1
8	69.3	7.7
9	89.8	6.7
10	65.9	8.0

6. Application to the Multiple Knapsack Problem

In the present section, we specialize the general framework of Section 4 to the multiple knapsack problem (MKP) (Pisinger, 1999; Scholl et al., 1997). This is a natural generalization of the traditional knapsack problem (Martello and Toth, 1990), where multiple knapsacks are available. Given a set of n items with weights w_j and profits p_j , and m knapsacks with capacity C_i , MKP reads

$$\max \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n p_j x_{ij} \tag{19}$$

$$\forall i \in \{1, \dots, m\} \quad \sum_{j=1}^n w_j x_{ij} \leq C_i \tag{20}$$

$$\forall j \in \{1, \dots, n\} \quad \sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij} \leq 1 \tag{21}$$

$$x \in \{0, 1\}^{m \times n} \tag{22}$$

where binary variable x_{ij} is set to 1 if and only if item j is loaded into knapsack i . We assume that all m knapsacks are identical and have the same capacity C , and we allow some items to also be identical, although this is not strictly required.

When applied to problem MKP, the orbital shrinking reformulation Q reads

$$\max \sum_{k=1}^K p_k y_k \tag{23}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K w_k y_k \leq mC \tag{24}$$

$$\forall k \in \{1, \dots, K\} \quad 0 \leq y_k \leq |V_k| \tag{25}$$

$$y \in \mathbb{Z}_+^K \tag{26}$$

Intuitively, in Q we have a general integer variable y_k for each set of identical items and a single knapsack with capacity mC . Given a solution y^* , the corresponding $R(y^*)$ is thus a one dimensional bin packing instance, whose task is to check whether the selected items can indeed be packed into m bins of capacity C .

To solve the bin-packing problem above, we propose two different approaches. The first approach is to deploy a standard compact CP model based on the global **binpacking** constraint (Shaw, 2004) and exploiting the CDBF (Gent and Walsh, 1997) branching scheme for search and symmetry breaking. Given an aggregated solution y^* , we construct a vector s with the sizes of the items picked by y^* , and sort it in non-decreasing order. Then we introduce a vector of variables b , one for each item: the value of b_j is the index of the bin where item j is placed. Finally, we introduce a variable l_i for each bin, whose value is the load of bin i . The domain of variables l_i is $\{0, \dots, C\}$. With this choice of variables, the model reads:

$$\text{binpacking}(b, l, s) \tag{27}$$

$$b_{j-1} \leq b_j \quad \text{if } s_{j-1} = s_j \tag{28}$$

where (28) are symmetry breaking constraints.

The second approach is to consider an extended model, akin to the well known Gilmore and Gomory column generation approach for the cutting stock problem (Gilmore and Gomory, 1961). Given the objects in y^* , we generate all feasible packings p of a single bin of capacity C . Let P denote the set of all feasible packings and, given packing p , let a_{pk} denote the number of items of type k picked. The corresponding model is

$$\sum_{p \in P} a_{pk} x_p = y_k^* \quad \forall k \tag{29}$$

$$\sum_{p \in P} x_p = m \tag{30}$$

$$x_p \in \mathbb{Z}_+ \tag{31}$$

where integer variables x_p count how many bins are filled according to packing p . In the following, we will denote this model with **BPcg**. Model **BPcg** is completely symmetry free, but it needs an exponential number of columns in the worst case.

6.1. Computational Experiments

We implemented our codes in C++, using the same hardware and software of Section 5.

In order to generate hard MKP instances, we followed the systematic study in (Pisinger, 2005). More details about our instance generation procedure can be found in (Salvagnin, 2013). In order to have a reasonable test set, we considered instances with a number of items $n \in \{30, 40, 50\}$ and number of knapsacks $m \in \{3, 4, 5, 6\}$. For each pair of (n, m) values, we generated 10 random instances following the procedure mentioned above, for a total of 120 instances. All the instances are available from the authors upon request. For each set of instances, we report aggregate results comparing the shifted geometric means of the number of branch-and-cut nodes and the computation times of the different methods. Note that we did not use specialized solvers, such as ad-hoc codes for knapsack or bin packing problems, because the overall scheme is very general and using the same (standard) optimization packages in all the methods allows for a clearer comparison of the different approaches.

As a first step, we compared 2 different pure MIP formulations. One is the natural formulation (19)–(22), denoted as `cpxorig`. The other is obtained by aggregating the binary variables corresponding to identical items. The model, denoted as `cpx`, reads

$$\max \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^K p_j z_{ik} \quad (32)$$

$$\forall i \in \{1, \dots, m\} \quad \sum_{k=1}^K w_j z_{ik} \leq C \quad (33)$$

$$\forall k \in \{1, \dots, K\} \quad \sum_{i=1}^m z_{ik} \leq U_k \quad (34)$$

$$z \in \mathbb{Z}_+^{m \times K} \quad (35)$$

where U_k is the number of items of type k . Note that `cpx` would be obtained automatically from formulation `cpxorig` by applying the orbital shrinking procedure if the capacities of the knapsacks were different. While one could argue that `cpxorig` is a modeling mistake, the current state-of-the-art in preprocessing is not able to derive `cpx` automatically, while orbital shrinking would. A comparison of the two formulations is shown in Table 3. As expected, `cpx` clearly outperforms `cpxorig`, solving 82 instances (out of 120) instead of 65. However, `cpx` performance is rapidly dropping as the number of items and knapsacks increases.

Then, we compared three variants of the hybrid MIP/CP procedure described in Section 6, that differs on the models used for the feasibility check. The first variant, denoted by `BPstd`, is based on the compact model (27)–(28). The second and the third variants are both based on the extended model (29)–(31), but differs on the solver used: a CP solver for `BPcgCP` and a MIP solver for

Table 3: Comparison between `cpxorig` and `cpx`.

n	m	# solved		time (s)		nodes	
		<code>cpxorig</code>	<code>cpx</code>	<code>cpxorig</code>	<code>cpx</code>	<code>cpxorig</code>	<code>cpx</code>
30	3	10	10	1.16	0.26	3,857	1,280
30	4	9	10	12.28	3.42	65,374	16,961
30	5	6	8	291.75	79.82	2,765,978	1,045,128
30	6	7	7	108.83	48.05	248,222	164,825
40	3	9	10	19.48	2.72	103,372	9,117
40	4	8	8	351.07	35.56	3,476,180	421,551
40	5	2	3	2,905.70	1,460.95	25,349,383	23,897,899
40	6	3	5	308.29	234.19	626,717	805,007
50	3	6	9	70.73	12.44	259,099	32,310
50	4	2	7	1,574.34	254.58	8,181,128	4,434,707
50	5	0	2	3,600.00	700.69	26,017,660	4,200,977
50	6	3	3	308.29	307.98	586,400	1,025,907

Table 4: Comparison between hybrid methods.

n	m	BPstd	# solved		time (s)			nodes		
			BPcgCP	BPcgMIP	BPstd	BPcgCP	BPcgMIP	BPstd	BPcgCP	BPcgMIP
30	3	10	10	10	0.07	0.05	0.05	245	270	270
30	4	10	10	10	0.18	0.12	0.08	157	160	160
30	5	10	10	10	1.28	0.26	0.14	90	88	88
30	6	10	10	10	1.24	0.25	0.13	42	40	40
40	3	10	10	10	0.64	0.42	0.17	502	540	540
40	4	10	10	10	0.54	0.20	0.17	225	224	224
40	5	9	10	10	8.63	1.20	0.62	202	225	225
40	6	8	10	10	17.96	1.65	0.46	48	60	60
50	3	10	10	10	1.59	0.93	0.44	837	914	914
50	4	10	10	10	4.06	1.11	0.60	337	335	335
50	5	6	8	10	137.52	23.97	3.58	172	245	335
50	6	7	7	10	17.15	12.73	2.85	17	16	140

BPcgMIP. All variants use model (23)–(26) as a master problem, which is fed to CPLEX and solved with dual reductions disabled, to ensure correctness of the method. CPLEX callbacks are used to implement the decomposition. A comparison of the three methods is given in Table 4. Note that the number of nodes reported for hybrid methods refers to the master only — the nodes processed to solve the feasibility checks are not added to the count, since they are not easily comparable, in particular when a CP solver is used. Of course the computation times refer to the whole solving process (slaves included). According to the table, even the simplest model BPstd clearly outperforms `cpx`, solving 110 instances (28 more) and with speedups up to two orders of magnitude. However,

as the number of knapsacks increases, symmetry can still be an issue for this compact model, even though symmetry breaking is enforced by constraints (28) and by CDBF. Replacing the compact model with the extended model, while keeping the same solver, shows some definite improvement, increasing the number of solved instances from 110 to 115 and further reducing the running times. Note that for the instances in our testbed, the number of feasible packings was always manageable (at most a few thousands) and could always be generated by Gecode in a fraction of a second. Still, on some instances, the CP solver was not very effective in solving the feasibility model. The issue is well known in the column generation community: branching on variables x_p yields highly unbalanced trees, because fixing a variable x_p to a positive integer value triggers a lot of propagations, while fixing it to zero has hardly any effect. In our particular case, replacing the CP solver with a MIP solver did the trick. Indeed, just solving the LP relaxation was sufficient in most cases to detect infeasibility. **BPcgMIP** is able to solve all 120 instances, in less than four seconds (on average) in the worst case. The reduction in the number of nodes is particularly significant: while **cpx** requires millions of nodes for some classes, **BPcgMIP** is always solving the instances in fewer than 1,000 nodes.

Finally, Table 5 shows the average gap closed by the OSR relaxation with respect to the initial integrality gap, and the corresponding running times (obtained by solving the orbital shrinking relaxation with a black box MIP solver, without the machinery developed in this section). According to the table, orbital shrinking yields a much tighter relaxation than standard linear programming, while still being very cheap to compute.

Table 5: Average gap closed by orbital shrinking and corresponding time.

n	m	gap closed	time (s)
30	3	45.3%	0.007
30	4	46.6%	0.004
30	5	42.8%	0.004
30	6	54.4%	0.002
40	3	48.4%	0.013
40	4	67.2%	0.007
40	5	55.3%	0.005
40	6	58.6%	0.003
50	3	52.7%	0.031
50	4	64.5%	0.030
50	5	61.1%	0.006
50	6	76.7%	0.003

7. Conclusions

We discussed a new methodology for deriving a relaxation of symmetric discrete optimization problems, based on variable aggregation within orbits.

The approach, called orbital shrinking, sometimes leads to an exact and symmetry-free reformulation of a given problem. In other cases, orbital shrinking produces just a relaxation of the original problem, so it needs to be embedded in a more general solution scheme. We have described a master-slave framework akin to Benders’ decomposition, where orbital shrinking acts as the master problem and generates a sequence of aggregated solutions to be checked for feasibility by a suitable slave subproblem — possibly based on Constraint Programming. Computational results on two specific applications prove the effectiveness of the scheme.

Future work should be devoted to the study of sufficient conditions under which orbital shrinking produces an exact reformulation. Practical applications of orbital shrinking decomposition to other symmetric problems are also worth investigating.

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